

4 IEROGLIFLI YAPON IBORALARIDA MA'NO O'ZGARISHI NATIJASIDA SONLARNING LEKSIK MA'NOSINING YO'QOLISHI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada yapon tili o'rganuvchilariga yapon iboralaridagi sonlarda leksik ma'no o'zgarishi va ularga sabab bo'ladigon omillarni o'rganishda va bular haqida ma'lumot berishda yordam beradi. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi so'zdagi o'zgarishlarni, yapon tilidagi sonlar qatnashgan 4 ieroglifli iboralarda tahlil qilish orqali tili o'rganuvchilarga ma'lumot beradi. Tadqiqot jarayonida yapon tilidagi 『ことわざと慣用句辞典』 (kotowaza to kanyouku jiten) “Maqol va iboralar lug'ati” va 『四字熟語辞典』 (yojijyukugo jiten) “4 ieroglifli iboralar luga'ti” dan “1, 10, 100, 1000” sonlari qatnashgan 81ta 4 ieroglifli iboralar tanlab olinadi va ushbu sonlardagi leksik ma'noning yo'qolishi orqali yuzaga kelgan yangi ma'nolarni aniqlaydi.

Ma'lumki, O'zbekistonda ingliz, nemis, arab, xitoy kabi bir qancha tillar bilan bir qatorda yapon tiliga bo'lgan qiziqish ham oshib bormoqda. Hozirgi kunga kelib oliy o'quv yurtlari bilan bir qatorda yapon tilini o'rgatuvchi bir qancha maxsus kurslar, yapon tili markazlari faoliyat yuritib kelmoqda. Oliy o'quv yurtlarida yapon tili nafaqat shunchaki muloqat uchun, balki chuqur o'rgatilib, turli yo'nalishlarda tadqiqotlar o'tkazilmoqda. Hozirgi kunda yapon tili jahonning 130 ta davlatida o'rganilib, O'zbekiston bu borada yapon tili o'rganuvchi o'quvchilar soni jihatidan 35-o'rinda turadi¹. Bu dunyo miqyosida yuqori ko'rsatkich hisoblanadi.

Mustaqillik yillarida o'zbek tilshunosligida frazeologizmlarning badiiy va publistik nutq uslublarida qo'llanish xususiyatlarini o'rganish bo'yicha ham muayyan ishlar amalga

¹ Yaponiyaning O'zbekistondagi favqulotda va muxtor elchisi Kato Fumihiko nutqidan, 14.11.2014

oshirildi. Jumladan, B. Yo‘ldoshevning “Frazeologik uslubiyat asoslari” (1999), B.Yo‘ldoshev, Z. Shodievlarning “Ufq” trilogiyasining lingvopoetik tahlili masalalari (2006)yapon tilida qilingan iborali ilmiy ishlardan misol keltir! kabi ishlar bu jihatdan e‘tiborga molik. Yapon tilini chet tili sifatida o‘rganuvchilar uchun mo‘ljallangan o‘quv qo‘llanmalarida iboralar deyarli keltirilmaydi.

Bu esa, o‘z navbatida, o‘quvchilar tomonidan yapon tilini mukammal o‘zlashtira olmasligidan dalolat beradi. Iboralar ikki tilda ham ko‘plab ishlatilishini hisobga olsak, ularni bilmay turib, yapon tilida nafaqat fikr bayon qilish, balki hozirgi zamon talablaridan biri bo‘lmish, tarjima qilish ham mushkul albatta. Ushbu ilmiy ishda o‘quvchilarga oz bo‘lsa-da, yapon tilidagi 4 ieroglifli iboralar hamda ushbu iboralarda so‘zlarning ma‘no o‘zgarishi haqida ma‘lumot berish maqsadida ham 4 ieroglifli iboralarda sonlarning ma‘no kategoriyasi tadqiq etiladi.

So‘zning ma‘no o‘zgarishi – vaqt o‘tishi bilan so‘zning ma‘nosi asl leksik ma‘nosidan boshqa ma‘noga o‘zgarishidir². Har bir so‘z birikmalarining semantic tizimida bir so‘z harakatlari boshqa so‘zlarga ta‘sir qiladi va yangi ma‘no tizimini yaratadi. So‘zning semantic o‘zgarish muammosi odatda bitta so‘zni topib uni muammoga aylantiradi, ammo semantic o‘zgarish muammosi muntazam ravishda olinishi kerak

Ma‘no o‘zgarishi o‘z ichiga ma‘no ko‘chishi, ma‘no torayishi, ma‘no kengayishi kabi hodisalarni qamrab oladi.

So‘zning ma‘no o‘zgarishi vaqtida so‘zning leksik ma‘nosi bilan yangi ma‘nosi o‘rtasida qandaydir bog‘liqlik bo‘ladi. Masalan, “shishaning og‘zi” “og‘iz” so‘zining asl ma‘nosi “ovqat yeydigan”, “tovush chiqaradigan joy”. Bu misolda ma‘nolar o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlik bor³.

So‘z quyidagi 3 sababga ko‘ra o‘zgaradi:

1. Lingvistik sababga ko‘ra. Bunda tilning o‘zi o‘zgarishga sabab bo‘ladi. Masalan, 「とて も」 (totemo) “juda” so‘zi ham ijobiy ham salbiy natijalarni ifodalashga nisbatan foydalaniladi. Biroq, asosan ijobiy narsalarga 「たいへん」 (taihen) “juda yaxshi” so‘zi ishlatiladi. Bundan

² Qarang: 言語学辞典 p.310

³中野弘三 (2012) 『意味論』 p.120

tashqari, 「よい運」 (yoi unn) “yaxshi omad” so’zi 「運」 (unn) “omad” so’zining o’zi bilan ifodalanmoqda. Chunki “omad” so’zining o’zi ijobiy ma’noni ifodalaydi. Shu orqali ma’no o’zgartirilmasdan, so’zning shaklini qisqartiriladi.

2. Ijtimoiy sababga ko’ra. Bunda ijtimoiy tizim, madaniyat, urf-odatlar, turmush tarzi va boshqalar ma’no o’zgarishiga sabab bo’ladi. Masalan, “Mashina” so’zining asl ma’nosi g’ildirak orqali harakatlanib, odam va narsalarni tashlaydigan vositadir. Yapon tilida ushbu so’zning ma’nosi o’zgarmagan. Biroq, Xeyan davrida 「牛車」 (ushiguruma) “buqa qo’shilgan arava”, Edo davrida 「荷車」 (niguruma) “arava”, Meiji va Taysha davrlarida 「人力車」 (jinrikishya) “inson boshqaradigan arava” va hozirda esa 「自動車」 (jidoushya) “avtomobil” deb nomlanadi.

3. Psixologik sababga ko’ra. O’zaro bog’liqlik va cheklash orqali hamkorga nisbatan ta’sir ko’rsatish orqali yuzaga keladigan sabab. Masalan, Yaponiyadagi to’ylardagi yopilish marosimi 「お開き」 (ohiraki) deb nomlanadi. Ya’ni, tugash, yopilish ma’nosini ifodalaydi va bu inson psixologiyasiga tugagan degan ma’no orqali ta’sir qiladi.

Yuqoridagilardan so’zning o’zgarishining 3 sababi bor ekanligi bilindi. Ya’ni, lingvistik sabab, ijtimoiy sabab, psixologik sababdir. Ijtimoiy sababga ko’ra, so’z turmush tarzi, urf-odatlar ta’siri orqali o’zgaradi. Psixologik sabab esa, insonlarning fikrlashi, o’ylashi orqali o’zgaradigan sababdir.

「四字熟語」 (yojijyukugo) 4 ieroglifli iboralarni eshitgandan, eslab qolinadigan ierogliflar kombinatsiyasi ko’pincha torayadi. Ierogliflar kombinatsiyalarida 4 harfli juda ko’p ma’noga ega so’zlar mavjud. Bu hozirgi vaziyatda ko’p ixtisoslashgan. Hatto, 「四字熟語」 (yojijyukugo) keng ma’noda 4 xil fe’l-atvor, tor ma’noda esa, 4 belgili iboralar tushunchasini ifodalaydi⁴.

Mazkur ilmiy maqolada yapon tilidagi 『ことわざと慣用句辞典』 (kotowaza to kanyoku jiten) “Maqol va iboralar lug’ati” va 『四字熟語辞典』 (yojijyukugo jiten) “4 ieroglifli iboralar luga’ti” dan “1, 10, 100, 1000 ” sonlari qatnashgan 81ta 4ieroglifli

⁴朝日新聞 『創作四字熟語』 2004年12月10日

iboralar tanlab olinib, tahlil qilindi va ma'no o'zgarishi orqali leksik ma'nosi yo'qotilgan son ishtirok etgan iboralar aniqlandi.

1. 心機一轉 (Shinki itten)

Iboraning ma'nosi: Biror narsani yangi kayfiyat bilan boshlash

“1” sonining ma'nosi: Bu yerda “1” ning asl ma'nosi yo'qolib, “yangi” degan ma'noni ifodalamoqda.

2. 大喝一声 (Taikatsu issei)

Iboraning ma'nosi: Baland ovozda tanbeh bermoq.

“1” sonining ma'nosi: Bu yerda “1” soni ovoz darajasini ifodalamoqda.

3. 驚馬十駕 (doba jyuuga)

Iboraning ma'nosi: Iqtidori bo'lmagan odam ham harakat qilsa, is'tedodli kishilar qilgan ishni qila oladi.

“10” sonining ma'nosi: Bu yerda “10” soni leksik ma'nosini yo'qotgan.

4. 十死一生 (Jyushi ishshou)

Iboraning ma'nosi: Saqlab qolish imkoniyati qariyib kam bo'lgan holatlarda ham ehtiyot qiling.

“10” sonining ma'nosi: Bu iborada “10” leksik ma'nosini yo'qotib, “qariyib” degan ma'noni ifodalamoqda.

5. 百發百中 (Hyappatsu hyakuchyu)

Iboraning ma'nosi: Orzuning aniq ushalishi.

“10” sonining ma'nosi: Bu iborada “100” soni leksik ma'nosini yo'qotib, kontekstdan kelib chiqqan holda “aniq” degan ma'noni ifodalamoqda.

6. 百依百順 (Hyakuyasushi hyakujun)

Iboraning ma'nosi: Odamlarga aytilganiga amal qilish.

“10” sonining ma’nosi: Bu iborada ham “100” soni o’z ma’nosini ifodalamasdan, umuman boshqa ma’noda ishlatilmoqda.

7. 千古不易 (Senko fueki)

Iboraning ma’nosi: O’tmisho’zgarmaydi.

“1000” sonining ma’nosi: Bu iborada “1000” soni asl ma’nosini yo’qotib, o’tmish degan ma’noni ifodalamoqda.

8. 惡事千里 (Akuji senri)

Iboraning ma’nosi: Yaxshi xabar unchalik bilinmaydi, lekin yomon xabar uzoqqa tez tarqaladi.

“1000” sonining ma’nosi: Bu yerda “1000” soni leksik ma’nosini yo’qotib, “uzoq masofa” degan ma’noni ifodalamoqda.

Ushbu tahlil natijasida 4 ieroglifli iboralarda “1, 10, 100, 1000” sonlarining leksik ma’nosi yo’qolishi orqali yuzaga kelgan yangi ma’nolari tahlil qilindi. “1” sonining leksik ma’nosi yo’qolib, (ovoz tonini, yangi) degan ma’nolarni ifodalashi aniqlandi. “10” sonining (tez, qariyib) kabi yangi ma’nolarni ifodalashi tahlil qilindi. “100” sonining leksik ma’nosi yo’qolib, (aniq) degan ma’noni ifodalanishi aniqlandi. Bundan tashqari, “1000” sonining yangi (uzoq, o’tmish, butun, abadiy) kabi ma’nolari tahlil qilinib, aniqlandi.

Yuqorida bayon qilingan fikr va tahlillardan quyidagi xulosalar chiqarildi:

Yapon tilida so’zlar 3 sababga ko’ra o’zgarishi ma’lum bo’ldi. Bular lingvistik sabab, ijtimoiy sabab va psixologik sabablardir. Bundan tashqari, yapon tilidagi 4 ieroglifli iboralarda “1, 10, 100, 1000” sonlarining ma’nolarini 3 guruhga bo’lib, tahlil qilindi. Bular sonlarning leksik ma’nolari, yasama ma’nolari va asl ma’no yo’qolishi natijasida yuzaga kelgan yangi ma’nolardir. Umumlashtirib aytadigan bo’lsak, “1, 10, 100, 1000” sonlari 4 ieroglifli iboralarda faqat leksik ma’noni ifodalabgina qolmasdan, kontekstga qarab yangi ma’noni ifodalashi ma’lum bo’ldi.

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METAPHORICAL MODELS IN LEGAL MEDIA DISCOURSE

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Abstract: This article investigates the role of precedent-related phenomena as a type of intertextuality in conceptual metaphorisation in media discourse. This study examines the place of precedent-related phenomena within the general theory of intertextuality, establishing their characteristics and how they can be differentiated from other types of intertextuality, and also provides a general overview of existing theories that aim to describe how precedent-related phenomena function. Drawing on magazine articles, the study analyses two sets of examples: a) single references, and b) recurring references to one source domain through various precedent-related phenomena. In the second set of examples, the differential characteristics and attributes that are common for the references are outlined in order to formulate a hypothetical name for the source domain that would be shared by its constituents. The article concludes by discussing what potential cognitive effect such conceptual metaphors could have on the recipient of a media text, especially when the precedent-related phenomena that refer to them are placed in the dominant positions of the text (such as the heading, the subheading, or the concluding sentence).

Key words: Metaphor, cognitive effect, intertextuality, precedent-related phenomenon, media discourse.

Introduction. What is a metaphor? There is no exact definition of this term, one of the linguistic dictionaries gives the following concept: “Metaphor is a turn of speech consisting in the use of words and expressions in a figurative sense to define an object or phenomenon based on analogy, comparison or similarity.”

The term “metaphor” is not new, Aristotle first began to use it, and in his work “Poetics” gave it the following definition: “Metaphor is the transfer of a word with a change in meaning from gender to species, from species to gender, or from species to species, or by analogy” [1]. Thus, the concept under consideration, originating from the time of antiquity, has retained its significance in the modern world. For many centuries, this universal means of constructing a language has been of concern and interest to many linguists, such as S. R. Levin, N. D. Artyunova, A. P. Chudinov, A. N. Baranov and Yu. N. Karaulov and others .

Usually, when we hear the term "metaphor", we imagine its inextricable connection with fiction, in which it is used to create incredible artistic images, descriptions of the landscape and any other situation. However, this is not the only area of application of this turn of speech, according to the work of J. Lakoff and M. Johnson “Metaphors we live by”, the metaphor is organically inherent in language, it is an integral part of human thinking, with the help of which in speech, and then language, there are also various concepts are fixed [2]. E. Kh. Meshcheryakova believes that metaphors play an important role in our

speech, we use them and create them imperceptibly to ourselves. Thus, the metaphor can be found in fiction (heart of stone), in colloquial speech (golden hands), in journalistic (war of rumors) and scientific (vowel sounds) style.

Metaphors act as a means of emotional and aesthetic impact, they serve as a way of persuading and achieving an effect, by such an impact on the addressee. Publicism is one of the areas of application of metaphor in this vein. Here the metaphor is an important means of influencing the mind, emotions and will of people. The journalistic style is the mass media (newspapers, magazines), which are the main source of information about the world both in the professional, business and entertainment (leisure), sports, political and cultural spheres. The media constantly influence the consciousness, worldview of a person, his culture, and also directs and shapes public opinion.

A journalistic metaphor (as well as an artistic one) is the use of words rethought on the basis of figurative-associative similarity, which arises as a result of subjective perception, impression, sensation.

Contemporary media discourse constantly develops new forms of linguistic expression in order to attract readers and influence their world-view. Both intertextuality and metaphor are examples of such expressive means, and they have often been studied separately in media linguistics. Recently, though, there have been attempts to also investigate how they can function together in media discourse (Hart, 2017), as well as in literary (Shonoda, 2012; Sell, 2008) and political (Marlow, 1997) discourses. In previous works, the functions of precedent-related phenomena in media discourse have been studied (Velykoroda, 2012; Velykoroda, 2016). The aim of this article is to explore how intertextual references (in the form of precedent-related phenomena) can be used as source domains for metaphorical framing in media texts, and what effects these devices create by implicitly alluding to the attributes of these precedent-related phenomena.

In recent decades, numerous scholars have studied the role of metaphor in creating cognitive images. This imagery is best described through the theory of conceptual metaphor of G. Lakoff and M. Johnson (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980; Cameron, 2008; Coulson, 2001; Croft & Cruse, 2004; Fauconnier & Turner, 2008; Grady, 2007; Bystrov, 2014). Metaphor in contemporary linguistics is understood as “a linguistic representation that results from the shift in the use of a word or phrase from one context or domain in which it is expected to occur to another context or domain where it is not expected to occur, thereby causing semantic tension” (Charteris-Black, 2004, p. 21). Moreover, “metaphor’s pragmatic characteristic is that it is motivated by the underlying purpose of persuading”, and this purpose is primarily covert and reflects the speaker’s intentions within a certain context of use (Charteris-Black, 2005, p. 15). Although Charteris-Black (2005) mostly studied metaphor in political discourse, it can be assumed that since a lot of political discourse takes place in media, his views can also be applied to the analysis of media texts. This approach is especially significant for us in that it stresses the “covert” purpose of persuading; thus, we can claim that media authors also aim to influence recipients in ways that are not necessarily

realised by them, or of which they remain unaware. Recipients can, thus, draw conclusions while remaining unconscious of the linguistic mechanisms of persuasion applied by the author.

Bakhtin's theory provided a foundation for Julia Kristeva's (1980) theory of intertextuality, which is extensively used in literary studies to denote interconnections between different texts. According to Kristeva, "any text is constructed as a mosaic of quotations; any text is the absorption and transformation of another" (Kristeva, 1980, p. 66). Traditionally in literary studies, forms of intertextuality have included allusions, quotations, parody, pastiche, calque, among others. Yet, the complexity of the phenomenon definitely allows for setting out new types of connections between texts.

In Eastern-European linguistics, the term intertextuality had not been used until a few decades ago. Yet, linguists came up with a new term for intertextual references, which they called "precedent-related phenomena". Originally the term was introduced in the late 1980s by Yuriy Karaulov as "precedent-related texts" in his theory on linguistic persona. This term was useful and applicable in cultural studies, as it denoted texts:

- 1) which are cognitively and emotionally meaningful for speakers,
- 2) which are of a super-personal nature, that is they are well known in the larger environment of the speaker, including predecessors and contemporaries,
- 3) reference to these texts recurs in the discourse of this speaker (Karaulov, 1987, p. 216). Karaulov (1987) spoke predominantly about texts which were prominent and significant cultural phenomena, and references to which could be easily and effortlessly recognised by large numbers of speakers.

A decade later, in order to step away from an exclusively textual understanding of similar processes, linguists introduced the term "precedent-related phenomenon", which could refer both to verbal and non-verbal expressions or images of this nature (Krasnykh, 2002).

In addition, the style of journalism is characterized by the use of metaphor as a way of assessing the phenomena of the surrounding reality, the following groups of metaphors are distinguished, compared with: medicine (chronic unemployment); military theme (football division); construction (window to Europe); theatrical vocabulary (political farce), games and sports (important player), cooking (liberal cookbook) and others.

Using such turns in the media, expressiveness of the text is created, sharpness of the statement is given, public opinion is formed about the subject both in positive and negative tones. In addition, such phrases in the title of the article attract the attention of more people, due to their interest. The metaphor saturates the text and makes it more "attractive", for example, S. V. Tsynk notes that Solzhenitsyn, a publicist who uses metaphors, is characterized by "a wealth of associations, a tendency to emotional evaluation of ideas, phenomena, events; striving for effective communication.

Today it is difficult to imagine journalistic texts that do not use a metaphor, for example, in No. 58 of April 2, 2021 of the Russian newspaper Izvestia, the following

expression is used: “fantastic sentence” - this is the title of one of the articles [5]. It is impossible to understand what the author means by this expression without reading the content of the article. This is a good example of using metaphor to generate interest and capture the attention of readers.

Contemporary media discourse is abundant with such transformations, and readers are not only expected, but even invited to engage in this word play and to decipher the original formulation and interpret the actual wording. Such transformations are not necessarily possible with other forms of intertextual references, as some of them require accuracy and literality, while others may become unrecognisable as a result of these transformations.

Contemporary media texts have become a favourable environment for precedent-related phenomena, where they are used, reinterpreted, popularised, promoted and created. Media text is often described as “the proverbial tip of the iceberg: most of its implied or presupposed meanings remain ‘hidden’” (van Dijk, 1998, p. 31), and precedent-related phenomena are those units in the text that are capable of implying a lot of the “hidden” meaning by invoking associations with the situations or texts they refer to on the vertical level. A media text should be conceived “as a tissue of voices and traces of other texts, when we engage with it, we go into dialogue with them. In studying media texts, we need to be aware that they are dialogic, or embedded in a mesh of intertextuality” (Talbot, 2007, p. 63). The wider social impact of media is not just to do with how they selectively represent the world, though that is a vitally important issue; it is also to do with what sorts of social identities, what versions of “self” they project and what cultural values (be it consumerism, individualism or a cult of personality) these entail (Fairclough, 1995, p. 17). These cultural values are expressed through references to the works of literature, religious texts and cultural phenomena that are both dominant in a culture and are meaningful for language speakers who refer to them themselves and recognise other speakers’ references to them.

Conclusion. Thus, we can draw the following conclusion: Metaphor is an integral part of modern journalism. For the purpose of emotional and aesthetic impact on the addressee, journalists use a wide variety of means of speech expressiveness, where metaphors are most popular. Having conducted research in the field of the use of metaphor, it can be noted with confidence that it is necessary to create a figurative representation of objects, phenomena and various situations among readers, which, in turn, leads to a more complete understanding of the author's intention and disclosure of the meaning of the text.

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